

Evolution of Hysteresis Index based on 2-year Outdoor Testing

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Over the last two decades the efficiency of perovskite cells has almost doubled, reaching current values of 26.1 %. However, since the emergence of this technology the phenomenon of hysteresis, that is the difference in the current-voltage (J-V) scans noticed, was observed. This was initially overlooked by the scientific community, thus focussing on the scan with the more favourable efficiency results [1]. Overtime it was realised that the changes taking place within the system, causing the hysteretic effect could not be ignored, as they led to confusion on the performance of the perovskite device. This led to new measurement techniques to combat the phenomenon, by using slower rates of J-V scan during the studies, as well as by measuring the stabilized or steady-state photocurrent at the maximum power point (MPP) voltage. The hysteretic behaviour is still a controversial topic with respect to its origin, however it is important to continue studying it in order to unlock key information about this phenomenon.

During this study the perovskite mini-modules used were of the *p-i-n* architecture. The evolution of the hysteresis index was studied over a period of 2 years. Initially, it was noticed that the hysteresis index, increases with increasing temperature within a fixed irradiance range of 950-1050 W/m². Similarly, the hysteresis index also seems to increase with irradiance. However, it was noticed that the hysteresis index was larger in the morning than in the afternoon for the same irradiance values. This is thought to be due to enhanced performance during the morning hours, due to overnight recovery. Furthermore, the diurnal degradation of the hysteresis index is being studied as well as its effect with temperature.

[1] S. N. Habisreutinger, N. K. Noel, H. J. Snaith, ACS Energy Lett. 2018, 3, 2472–2476.

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